

Supplementary material: Reaction-driven formation of SiC–ZrC interlayers for high-strength joining of monolithic CVD β -SiC and SiC_f/SiC composites

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Fig. S1. Secondary SEM image and corresponding elemental maps of the CVD-SiC sample joined with $ZrSi_2$ at 1500 °C.

Fig. S2. Secondary SEM image and corresponding elemental maps of the CVD-SiC sample joined with $ZrSi_2$ at 1700 °C.

Fig. S3. Secondary SEM image and corresponding elemental maps of the CVD-SiC sample joined using a non-stoichiometric $ZrSi_2$ -C filler at 1500 °C.